

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

METHODS FOR DAMPING ELECTROMECHANICAL LOW-FREQUENCY OSCILLATIONS IN POWER SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The interconnection of power systems for parallel operation and the formation of power system interconnections lead to a change in the nature of the stability problem and can significantly affect the conditions for using inter-system electrical connections due to the occurrence of low-frequency oscillations that threaten the stable operation of such interconnections. The article proposes the author's list and reviews methods for damping low-frequency oscillations of operating parameters that have been successfully applied in practice in power systems and power unions.

Keywords: low-frequency oscillations, damping methods, PSS, FACTS, HVDC.

Introduction

The ongoing integration processes in the global electricity sector have led to the creation of large-scale power systems. Such power systems connect a large number of different types of power sources for parallel operation and supply electricity to a large number of consumers. Ensuring the stability of power system operations is a key requirement for their functioning, as disruptions to their stable operation can pose a threat to human life and result in significant economic losses. At the same time, in recent years, numerous incidents have been recorded in power systems across Europe, Asia, and the Americas, caused by the occurrence and subsequent amplification of low-frequency electromechanical oscillations with frequencies usually not exceeding 1 Hz:

- China (2012–2013) – frequencies around 0,31 Hz and 0,63 Hz [1];
- USA, WECC (2017–2018) – frequency around 0,4 Hz [2];
- Kazakhstan (2020) – frequency around 0,35 Hz [3];
- Ireland (2021) – frequencies around 0,08 Hz [4];
- India (2023) [5].

Low-frequency oscillations constantly occur in power systems or power grids. This is caused by the acceleration or deceleration of the rotors of synchronous machines, which depends on the imbalance between the input mechanical power and the output electrical power of these machines when consumption in the power system changes. These low-frequency oscillations can be observed in the graphs of power flow changes along power transmission lines connecting synchronous generators to consumer substations. At the same time, the presence of low-frequency oscillations in a power system does not always lead to a loss of stability.

Identification of dangerous low-frequency oscillations in terms of power system stability

According to Lyapunov, the stability of any system in the absence of input disturbances can be determined by the sign of the real part of the roots of the first equation of the system (1) at any equilibrium point:

$$\begin{cases} \Delta \dot{x} = A \cdot \Delta x + B \cdot \Delta u \\ \Delta y = C \cdot \Delta x + D \cdot \Delta u \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where:

x – vector of state variables (consisting primarily of the system's state parameters: rotor angles, angular velocities, electromotive forces etc.);

u – vector of control inputs;

y – vector of output signals, which reflect the result of the control inputs;

A – state matrix;

B – control matrix;

C – output matrix;

D – feedforward matrix.

The first equation of the system (1) will have Z solutions of the form corresponding to the dimension of the square state matrix A [6]:

$$Z_i = K_i \cdot e^{\lambda_i t}, \quad (2)$$

where:

K – complex amplitude;

λ – eigenvalue of matrix A ;

t – time;

n – dimension of matrix A ;

$i = 1 \dots n$.

The presence of complex-conjugate eigenvalues λ indicates the presence of oscillations in the system. In this case, the eigenvalues can be expressed as

$$\lambda = \sigma \pm j\omega, \quad (3)$$

where:

ω – angular frequency of oscillations (rad/s);

σ – the system's stability against oscillations with frequency ω (s^{-1}).

When assessing the threat posed by low-frequency oscillations in terms of the stability of the power system, the damping ratio is the most informative parameter among the various low-frequency oscillation parameters:

$$\xi = \frac{-\sigma}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + \omega^2}}. \quad (3)$$

Given the importance of the damping factor for low-frequency oscillations in power systems, the following types of low-frequency oscillations are distinguished:

- $\zeta > 0$ – damping low-frequency oscillations, whose amplitude decreases over time under the current operating conditions of the power system (relatively safe low-frequency oscillations);
- $\zeta = 0$ – non-damping low-frequency oscillations with a constant amplitude (dangerous low-frequency oscillations);
- $\zeta < 0$ – non-damping low-frequency oscillations with an amplitude that increases over time (very dangerous low-frequency oscillations).

In the context of ensuring the stability of the power system, special attention should be paid to damping sustained oscillations.

Methods for damping low-frequency oscillations in power systems

The author's analysis of the scientific and technical literature makes it possible to propose the following list of methods for damping low-frequency oscillations that pose a threat to the stability of power systems:

- flexible alternating current transmission systems (FACTS);
- high-voltage direct current (HVDC) systems;
- energy storage units (ESU);
- changing the settings of the automatic excitation controllers of synchronous generators;
- power system stabilizers (PSS).

FACTS devices are systems for series, parallel or combined connection, whose parameters can be adjusted quite rapidly using power electronics.

Examples of FACTS for series connection include Thyristor Controlled Series Capacitor (TCSC) and Static Series Synchronous Compensator (SSSC). The effectiveness of FACTS for series connection, in terms of significantly improving the damping of low-frequency oscillations, has been confirmed by research results on Brazilian power system where such devices installed at the Imperatriz and Serra da Mesa substations made it possible to change the damping of the 0.2 Hz low-frequency oscillation from negative to positive, which were observed in the "North–South" section following a sudden 300 MW reduction in power generation at the Tucuruí hydroelectric power plant in the Northern Power System of the Brazilian IPS [7]. Graphics of active power flow fluctuations in this section with the FACTS unit at the Imperatriz substation turned off and with the FACTS unit turned on are shown in Fig. 1. In both cases, the load on the "North–South" interconnection prior to the occurrence of the specified disturbance was 500 MW.

Examples of FACTS for parallel connection include Static Var Compensator (SVC) and Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM). The significant improvement in low-frequency oscillations damping in the power system resulting from the use of FACTS has been confirmed, in particular, by calculations performed on a model of the Eastern USA power system [8], where, as a result of a three-phase short circuit

Figure 1 – Active power low-frequency oscillations in the Brazilian power system without and with the series FACTS unit

lasting 0,083 s at the North Nashville substation, low-frequency oscillations with a frequency of approximately 0,6 Hz were observed. The graphics of active power fluctuations at unit №2 of the Gallatin power

plant in the absence of FACTS on the busbars of this power plant and in the presence of parallel connected FACTS with a capacity of 8 MVar and 50 MVar are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 – Active power low-frequency oscillations in the Western USA power system without and with the parallel FACTS unit

Examples of FACTS for combined connection include Unified Power Flow Controller (UPFC) and Convertible Static Compensator (CSC). The significant impact of UPFCs on damping low-frequency oscillations in power systems has been confirmed by the results of

studies conducted on model of the Nigerian power system [9]. Figure 3 show graphics of deviations in active power flow from pre-fault values preceded the occurrence of an unstable three-phase short circuit on one of the power transmission lines of the Nigerian power system without and with the UPFC.

Figure 3 – Active power deviation low-frequency oscillations of power transmission line in the Nigerian power system without and with the UPFC unit

The improved damping efficiency of low-frequency oscillations in the presence of HVDC systems has been confirmed by research results on power system models and examples of their application in real power systems. In particular, the use of a bipolar HVDC link with a nominal voltage of ± 500 kV in the Southeast Power System of the Mexican power system between the Temascal and MMT substations made it possible to change the damping of low-frequency oscillations with a frequency of about 0.5 Hz from negative to positive, which were observed in the “North–South”

section during an emergency outage of the 400 kV power line between the PDB and TEH substations [10]. Graphs of voltage modulus oscillations on the busbars of the Temascal substation in the absence of an HVDC link and with an HVDC link present in two operating modes are shown in Fig. 4.

The improved effectiveness of damping low-frequency oscillations using energy storage units (ESU) has been confirmed by the results of studies conducted using test

Figure 4 – Voltage module low-frequency oscillations at the Temascal substation in Mexico's power system without and with HVDC interconnection

models of power systems. In particular, for the test model of a four-machine IEEE 2-area benchmark system, the use of energy storage devices made it possible to change the damping of low-frequency oscillations with a frequency of about 0,5 Hz, which arose in the

230 kV interconnection, from negative to positive [11]. The graphics of active power flow oscillations across the interconnection in the absence of ESU and using ESU with different control methods are shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5 – Active power low-frequency oscillations in IEEE 2-area benchmark system with and without ESU

The effectiveness of damping low-frequency oscillations by adjusting the settings of the automatic voltage regulators of synchronous generators is demonstrated using a model of a four-machine test power system, for which reducing the voltage gain coefficients in

the automatic voltage regulator (AVR) from 200 to 10 made it possible to change the damping of low-frequency oscillations with a frequency of about 0,65 Hz, which arose in the interconnection, from negative to positive (Fig. 6) [12].

Figure 6 – Active power low-frequency oscillations damping improvement via decreasing gain coefficients of synchronous machines AVR

The primary function of PSS is to improve the damping of the low-frequency oscillations of generator rotors by regulating their excitation using auxiliary stabilizing signals, which are generated based on input signals of active power, angular velocity, frequency, or their deviations from a specific reference value. Currently, PSS is the most widely used method for damping low-frequency oscillations in electric machines. The effectiveness of their application in terms of improving low-frequency oscillations damping in power systems has been confirmed by the results of a series of studies conducted both on test models of power systems

and in real power systems. In particular, for the Brazilian Southern Power System the installation of four PSSs made it possible to significantly improve the damping of low-frequency oscillations with a frequency of approximately 1,2 Hz, which arose in the power system as a result of a sudden 5% increase in the input mechanical torque of the gas turbine connected to the Barracao substation busbars. The graphics of the rotor angular speed oscillations of the Salto Osorio hydropower plant generating unit with the PSSs deactivated in the Southern Power System of the Brazilian IPS and during their operation in two modes are shown in Fig. 7 [13].

Figure 7 – Rotor angular speed low-frequency oscillations damping without and with PSS

Conclusions

This article examines the issue of damping low-frequency oscillations in operating parameters that pose a threat to the stability of power systems, proposes a list of methods for damping these oscillations, and provides examples of how these methods are applied in practice. The selection of the proper method for damping low-frequency oscillations from the list provided should be based on an analysis of the structure of the power system and the parameters of the equipment within it that can affect the damping coefficient of these oscillations.

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